

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

PROJECT	
Project number:	101081782
Project acronym:	deCYPher
Project name:	Decipher cytochrome P450 enzymes (CYPs) by digital tools to produce flavonoids and terpenoids

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Date:	31/01/2024
Version:	V02.1

1. Data Summary

Datasets that will be re-used:

Dataset of CYP sequences of non-flowering plants provided by the group of Professor David R. Nelson. Format: commonly used formats and open formats (xlsx, csv).
 UniProt: Plants and bacteria CYP450-TMD dataset queried from UniProt database. Format: open (fasta, csv).
 AlphaFoldDB: Plants CYP450 protein structure available on AlphaFold database. Format: open (pdb).
 P450 Database: CYP entries available on The Plant Cytochrome P450 Database. Format: open (csv).
 BRENDA: Enzyme molecular and biochemical information: open format (txt, csv).
 BindingDB: Interactions between proteins and small ligands and drug-like molecules. Format: open (csv).

Additional existing databases of molecular (Gene, Protein, etc.) & chemical-physical characteristics (PubChem, ChEBI, etc.) of CYPs and of plants chemicals (e.g. flavonoids) will be queried and the results re-used, as well as existing sequences/designs of synthetic parts (SynBioHub, SEVA-DB, GS, etc.). Open formats will be used (e.g. csv, txt, fasta).

Code, model or software tool that will be re-used:

MEMSAT-SVM, Merizo, Mempack, MemEmbed, DeepTMPred, MEMSAT-SVM, colab notebook for DeepTMPred,
 Enzyme-substrate prediction DL model: ESP.
 Protein language models: ESM2, ProtT5, ProtGPT2.
 Protein design methods: Protein MPNN
 Multiple sequence alignment tools: Mafft, Clustal
 Sequence folding tools: ESMFold, AlphaFold2
 Protein frustration tools: FrustratometerR, FrustraEvo
 Genome-scale metabolic model: P. putida GEM iJN1462

New code, model or software tool that will be generated

M01-Model: Pipeline for CYP sequence design and feature extraction. Format: open (r/.py, .Rmd/.ipynb, xml/xlsx/json, PDBx/mmCIF).

New datasets that will be generated

Molecular & chemical-physical characteristics of CYPs and analysis of CYPs in microbial hosts (yeast, Rhodobacter, pseudomonas).
 D01-CYP genetic parts: synthetic parts sequences (DNA). Format: open formats such as gb, fasta.
 D02-CYP protein sequence. Format: open formats such as pdb/pdbqt, fasta, txt, mzIdentML, mzTab.
 D03 - CYP structure prediction. Format: open formats such as pdb, pkl.
 D04-Microscopy: images of CYP localisation. Format: czi and open formats such as tiff or jpeg.
 D05-Metabolomics: evaluation of metabolites production in microorganism. Formats: Agilent, MassHunter, raw, excel and open formats such as csv, mzml.
 D06-transcriptomic: for CYP functional expression level in microorganisms. Formats: open formats such as fastq, csv, tsv.

Raw data (such as images, chromatography and other omics datafiles) acquired in proprietary formats (e.g.

.eps,.ab1) will be converted to open formats (e.g. fastq, mzML) when possible. Processed data will be provided in open formats (e.g. .csv, .txt).

Existing and newly generated datasets and code will be used to design and train the ML/AI algorithm which will predict genetic sequences of CYP enzymes for efficient and accurate production of flavonoids and terpenoids.

Q01: questionnaire and survey. Format: open formats (pdf, csv). The survey will be used to capture the societal point of view about linking the power of AI/ML with the synthesis of (parts of) organisms.

B01: Book on reflection about convergence of AI and SynBio. Format: pdf.

T01: Templates and best practice. Format: open formats such as md, csv, tsv, json.

Currently, we estimate that altogether the data volume will be around 2TB.

The data on new CYP450 sequences optimized for efficient production of flavonoids and terpenoids, coupled with a machine learning/artificial intelligence model for generating such sequences, holds great potential for biotechnology companies, pharmaceutical industries, and industrial manufacturers. This information can drive advancements in synthetic biology, metabolic engineering, and drug discovery, benefiting research institutions, technology providers, and entrepreneurial ventures.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Throughout the project, unique persistent identifiers will be assigned to each record in a dataset on the DataHub platform and on the deCYPher NextCloud instance. Subsequently, each dataset will receive a persistent identifier from the repository in which it will be published.

Rich metadata will be provided according to repository requirements to allow discovery of the datasets. Different technologies-specific repositories enforce distinct metadata models; for instance, SDRF proteomics for PRIDE, MAGE-Tab, and SRA standards for nucleic acids sequencing experiments, and ISA for metabolomics experiments.

Keywords and other metadata fields will be provided in each repository to optimize the discovery of datasets. In addition, metadata will be available in DataHub platform to allow findability of the datasets. These repositories may expose these keywords and metadata for harvesting and indexing purposes.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

New code, models or software that will be generated will be published in Zenodo, WorkflowHub and GitHub. A unique identifier will be assigned. Mathematical models of biological systems might be published in BioModels, where an identifier will be assigned.

List of datasets and respective repositories:

D01-CYP genetic parts will be deposited in GoldenStandard database, ENA/GenBank or BCCM GeneCorner. An identifier will be generated. Physical plasmids could be made available via BCCM GeneCorner and CSIC internal database.

D02-CYP protein sequence will be deposited in UniProt and/or PRIDE database.

D03-CYP structures prediction will be deposited in Zenodo, ModelArchive or PDB-Dev databases.

D04-Microscopy images will be deposited to BiImage Archive or EMPIAR.

D05-Metabolomics will be deposited in MetaboLights.

D06-Transcriptomic will be published in ENA or ArrayExpress.

The questionnaire, the anonymised result and the book will be published in Zenodo or FigShare, and then made available via deCYPher and BioArt Society's website.

All repositories will provide a unique identifier for each entry and dataset.

Data:

The majority of datasets, code, models and software that will be re-used are already openly available under open licence. The condition for sharing the dataset provided as personal communication will be defined during the project. Some data generated by companies (e.g., Lantana Bio, Isobionics, ML6) and other partners in

deCYPher will be considered confidential within the consortium. The conditions and possibilities for sharing the related metadata will be defined during the project. The conditions to share the related metadata will be carefully considered, so that companies and other partners have the flexibility to retain data for commercial use or IP protection, while determining the extent and manner of data sharing.

Non-confidential data will be made openly available, after publication of a scientific article and/or have secured IP protection. The consortium will make the necessary arrangements in order to maintain the embargo on the data access until essential steps in securing intellectual property have been taken.

An open licence will be applied to ML/AI model developed in deCYPher, although the software package or executable software might be protected by patent for commercial use and made available under a proprietary licence (dual licencing).

The questions of the survey (Q01) will be made openly available; the resulting answers from citizens will be anonymised first, aggregated and then shared openly.

The digital book will be made openly available.

All digital data will be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol, such as URL from publications or website, and identifiers or access numbers from data repositories.

During the project, access to personal data related to the questionnaire (Q01) will be granted only to Biofaction partners (as described in the participants consent form) via the deCYPher instance of NextCloud, which requires personal authentication via individual logins.

Metadata:

Metadata will be shared together with the data via the repositories listed above, under the same open licences (CC0 or CC-BY-4.0). Metadata contains information to enable the user to access the data.

The repositories that will be used to share data and metadata aim to preserve access to both data and metadata permanently for the foreseeable future as part of the scientific record.

All data is accessible and readable by open-source software, as will be mentioned in the documentation if needed.

2.3. Making data interoperable

When applicable, existing ontologies will be utilized. For example, the ontology representation of the NCBI organismal taxonomy (NCBI taxon) will be used to define organisms. Genetic parts are described according to the Standard European Vector Architecture, the Golden Standard (GS) Type IIS assembly method underpinned by SEVA and developed by CSIC, and the MEMO Standard Assembly (MEMOSA) developed by UGent. Metadata and documentation for technology-specific experiments will adhere to the metadata vocabularies, standards, and formats required by the data repositories listed above.

The scientific links between referenced datasets will be described (qualified reference).

2.4. Increase data re-use

Available metadata fields in the data repositories used for publishing (meta)data will be utilized to provide the necessary documentation for data reuse and analysis validation. Detailed protocols, README files, and codebooks describing variables, units, missing data, etc., will be uploaded or referenced where possible. Additional documentation and metadata will be available in DataHub platform.

The code and models that are going to be generated will be available under open licences (e.g. BSD-3, MIT, etc.), although the software package or the executable software might be protected by patent for commercial use and will be made available under a proprietary licence (dual licencing).

Non-confidential scientific data will be made available via the repositories as listed above. The data will then be under the default open licence of the repository (e.g. CC0) or, where possible, a specific open licence will be indicated (CC-BY-4.0). This is in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement.

Data produced in deCYPher could be used by third parties after the end of the project, in accordance with the attached license and reuse conditions.

Throughout the project, data provenance will be extensively documented in README files stored alongside the data. Metadata templates used to compile the datasets will include provenance information, such as a

reference to the laboratory inventory system. Sample lineage in experiments will be recorded in DataHub following the ISA model. The provenance of data analysis workflows will be documented in GitHub and/or linked notebooks. When possible, provenance information will also be shared with the data in the repositories.

Each researcher or experimentalist, along with the designated senior researcher or principal investigator of that team, will be responsible for the quality of the data generated in day-to-day operations. Data quality will be controlled and documented through the use of ELN, LIMS, following SOPs, or equivalent systems and best practice guidelines in place in each laboratory. In addition, the Data Management Working Group (DMWG) in deCYPher will oversee the consistency and quality of data collection through the implementation of metadata templates in DataHub. These templates will include controlled vocabulary and apply data entry validation. The integrity of data files will be evaluated via checksum.

3. Other research outputs

Each researcher or experimentalist, along with the designated senior researcher or principal investigator of that team, will be responsible for the management, storage, and availability of physical materials that could be essential for the reproducibility of the results and/or considered research output. The availability of physical material after the project will be discussed and considered in the DMWG. If materials will be transferred among partners, a MTA will be considered and negotiated.

4. Allocation of resources

In deCYPher, the implementation of the FAIR principles for data and research outputs is a pivotal aspect of our data management strategy. The costs associated with making data FAIR involve various elements, including data and metadata storage during the project, data and metadata harmonization, data preservation and ensuring robust security measures. The project budget allocation includes provisions for these costs to ensure the comprehensive implementation of FAIR principles throughout the project.

In terms of responsibility for data management within the project, we have designated a dedicated Data Management Working Group (DMWG). This team is composed of individuals with expertise in data management as well as scientists in the field of biotechnology. Their primary role involves supervising the complete data lifecycle, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles and implementing protocols to facilitate standardized data collection and sharing among project members.

The work of the DMWG includes the creation of metadata templates within DataHub, provided by VIB, to harmonize data collection across all partners. Additionally, our chosen data storage solution is B2DROP, provided by BSC. B2DROP, a part of EUDAT's suite of services, is a secure and trustworthy data exchange service designed for researchers and scientists to share and store research data, and is not intended for personal, recreational, political, or commercial use. B2DROP is integrated with NextCloud. This service supports a variety of data types for scientific use, including temporary, primary, and processed data in numerous formats.

For long-term preservation, the plan is to share the research outputs in trusted repositories within the relevant domain of interest that do not incur fees for data publication and archival. This will occur once the project concludes, intellectual property rights are secured, and/or a scientific paper is published. The selection of the repositories will depend on the nature of the data (see above).

5. Data security

Data will be handled in accordance with the information security guidelines of each partner's institution, involving measures proportionate to their nature and the associated risks. Computers and external drives will be password-protected, and access to the rooms or labs where they are kept will be controlled. Regular security upgrades to operating systems will be performed. Systems used for sharing and storing data within the consortium during the project, such as DataHub at VIB, NextCloud instance at BSC, and SharePoint at UGent, are regularly backed up and password-protected.

Any access to the data related to citizens survey will be restricted only to the dedicated researcher and the involved PI (Markus Schmidt). Personal data will be pseudo-anonymised for the data analysis and anonymised and aggregated before data publication.

As mentioned before, B2DROP integrated with NextCloud is chosen for deCYPher as the data storage solution. B2DROP is designed to protect user data through multiple layers of protection, including data recovery, secure storage, and the transfer of sensitive information.

B2DROP emphasizes user privacy, allowing only the user and their chosen collaborators to access their data. However, in urgent situations, an administrator may access the files. The data is stored at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center. For data recovery, a systematic and reliable backup mechanism has been established. This includes regular and automated backups of the data stored in NextCloud to facilitate swift

recovery in the event of data loss or system failures.

Concerning secure storage and archiving, NextCloud provides advanced encryption features that safeguard data both at rest and in transit. Through robust encryption protocols, sensitive information is protected from unauthorized access, providing a secure environment for long-term storage.

The secure transfer of sensitive data is facilitated through NextCloud's encryption protocols and secure communication channels. Data transfer is conducted by using protocols such as HTTPS and WebDAV. External exchanges are conducted using encryption methods to prevent interception and unauthorized access during transit.

In addressing the long-term preservation and curation of our data, we will use trusted repositories where the data will be securely stored. These repositories will adhere to community standards for data preservation and curation, ensuring that our data remains accessible, authentic, and usable over an extended period.

6. Ethics

The condition for data sharing and long term preservation will be disclosed to the participants in the informed consent. Data related to the citizens survey will be anonymised before publication of the results.

The consortium will adhere to ethical principles and relevant legislation concerning personal data, AI/ML, and GMO, as outlined in the Ethics section of the proposal. No foreseeable ethical or legal issues are anticipated to affect the sharing of the data.

7. Other issues

Each partner will comply with institutional or company best practices and procedures for data management that are in line with and complementary to the ones highlighted in this DMP.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
01.0	15.01.2024	Initial draft created by Flora D'Anna and Laura Silva Portell
01.1	24.01.2024	Modified section 2.2 by Marjan De Mey and Lien De Wannemaeker
01.2	25.01.2024	First feedback included by Flora
02.0	30.01.2024	Flora D'Anna and Laura Silva Portell included all feedback; final version to be sent for review
02.1	31.01.2024	Flora D'Anna finalised the layout by removing the guidelines of the template (green text).